

POLICY BRIEF

FROM DATA COLLECTION TO DATA USE: STRENGTHENING DECISION-MAKING AT SUBNATIONAL LEVELS IN MALAWI

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Authors: Louiss Saddick, David Zingwe, Juliana Zungu, Esme Kadzamira, Halima Twabi, Paul Chiwaya and Martin Mwale

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Notes

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Reviewers

Rashid Iwiire and Nafisa Waziri

About the Unlocking Data Initiative

The Unlocking Data Initiative is a community of practice that connects African scholars, NGOs, national statistics offices and policymakers for the purpose of improving access to and use of education data. The **Unlocking Data: Scaling Uses and Users of Education Data** project is a collaborative work led by Zizi Afrique Foundation and supported by Education Sub-Saharan Africa, eBase Africa, and the University of Malawi's Centre for Education Research and Training (CERT). The latter project, which is being implemented in Cameroon, Kenya and Malawi, aims to scale up uses and users of data to address the knowledge gap of how to adaptively scale up the effective use of existing education data by policymakers and researchers in Africa.

To find out more about us, go to <https://unlockingdata.africa/>. Our evidence library can be found at <https://docs.unlockingdata.africa/lib/>

Key Messages

- Education data is widely collected in Malawi, but rarely used for decision-making processes such as planning, resource allocation, learner support, and school improvement at the school, zone, and district levels, highlighting the need to strengthen data-informed decision-making systems.
- Evidence from national studies, cohort tracking workshops at the subnational level, and stakeholder consultations shows that the main challenge is not the availability of data but the limited capacity and institutional mechanisms to translate data into action.
- Limited use of education data weakens planning processes, contributes to resource misallocation, and slows improvements in learning outcomes.
- Key barriers to effective data use include limited data literacy, fragmented information systems, weak feedback loops, and low incentives for evidence-based decision-making.
- Strengthening education data use in Malawi requires sustained investment in skills, integrated information systems, accountability mechanisms, and supportive leadership structures that promote evidence-based planning and decision-making.

1. Introduction

Malawi's education system generates substantial data through the annual school census, cohort tracking, routine administrative reporting, and national surveys ([↑Kadzamira et al., 2025](#)). Schools, zones, and districts regularly collect information on enrolment, attendance, staffing, infrastructure, repetition, dropout learner progression, and learning outcomes.

Despite this, data use at subnational levels remains limited, with planning processes still largely driven by reporting requirements rather than evidence-based decision-making ([↑Saddick et al., 2025](#); [↑Twabi et al., 2025](#)). Recent decentralisation reforms and improvements in digital infrastructure present an opportunity to strengthen local data use.

In practice, this weak data use means that key decisions at school, zone, and district levels in Malawi are often not sufficiently informed by available administrative and learning data, limiting the responsiveness of planning processes to actual system needs. Without effective use of data to inform decisions, inefficiencies in resource allocation and persistent learning gaps are likely to continue despite the availability of extensive data systems. Effective use of education data is critical for improving targeting of interventions, teacher deployment and management, equity in resource allocation, accountability, and school improvement planning ([↑World Bank, 2023](#)).

Although cohort tracking within the Education Management Information System (EMIS) provides a mechanism for generating longitudinal learner-level data, its use in routine planning and decision-making at school, zone, and district levels remains limited in Malawi. Cohort tracking involves monitoring and evaluating the performance of a group of learners over time through the assignment of Learner Identification Numbers (LINs) to pupils upon entry into school ([↑Twabi et al., 2025](#)). This limited use reflects a broader challenge of underutilising available education data to support evidence-based planning and learner support.

The Unlocking Data Initiative in Malawi engaged teachers and other key stakeholders through consultation meetings. The Unlocking Data Initiative in Malawi engaged stakeholders, including teachers, through consultation meetings aimed at strengthening the use of cohort tracking data for planning, monitoring, and improving learner support at subnational levels.

2. Our Findings

Evidence from subnational cohort tracking workshops, the Malawi Situational Analysis Report ([↑Kadzamira et al., 2025](#)), the Evidence Gap Map ([↑Saddick et al., 2025](#)), and stakeholder consultations suggests that the key challenge at school, zone, and district levels is not limited data availability but the weak use of available data for planning and decision-making. The findings below illustrate how this data-use challenge is reinforced by institutional, technical, and capacity-related constraints.

- Data is routinely collected but rarely used at the school and district levels. Despite extensive data collection at lower levels, data is not routinely analysed or used for school-, zone-, or district-level planning and management. Therefore, decision-making at local levels remains only weakly supported by systematic evidence, relying on experience or informal judgement.
- Data quality is weakened by limited use and analysis at local levels. Because data is rarely used for decision-making, incentives for accuracy, validation, and completeness are low, resulting in poor-quality data that further limits its use. This is evident with cohort tracking data, which has rarely been analysed since 2012 and, as a result, is currently difficult to use for effective planning.

When data is not used, incentives to maintain accurate and complete records weaken, reducing data quality and further limiting its usefulness for planning.

- Data collection is primarily driven by reporting and compliance requirements, not local decision-making needs. School-level data is gathered primarily for reporting to higher authorities rather than for local use in planning and improvement at school, zone, and district levels.

- Subnational actors have limited capacity to analyse and interpret data for planning purposes. School leaders, zonal supervisors, and district officials need sustained support in basic data literacy, analysis, interpretation and use of findings in planning.
- Data systems are fragmented, paper-based, and poorly integrated, limiting usability. Parallel data collection systems, inconsistent formats, and reliance on paper-based records lead to duplication, data quality issues, and limited accessibility across schools, zones, districts, and the central Ministry. During a subnational workshop on improving data collection tools for cohort tracking involving headteachers, Zonal Education Management Information System (ZEMIS) officers, and District Education Management Information System (DEMIS) officers from Dedza, Machinga and Zomba districts, a headteacher said:

“The Ministry of Education no longer provides standardised registers to schools. Schools are forced to make their own, leading to inconsistencies and non-ideal record keeping.”
- Feedback mechanisms are weak, resulting in one-way data flows from schools to the zone to the district level, and this has become institutionalised. Data collected from schools and sent to districts is not routinely analysed at that level. As a result, there is limited feedback from zones or districts to schools.

These findings together point to a systemic disconnect between data collection and data use within subnational education planning and management processes.

3. Why Data Remain Unused

Constraint	Evidence from Findings	Implication	What should change
Limited data literacy	Low capacity to analyse and interpret data	Weak evidence use in planning	Need for strengthened data literacy and analytical capacity among school, zone and district officials
Reporting-oriented culture	Data collected for compliance	Data not used for decision-making	Shift towards decision-oriented data use within EMIS and school systems
Fragmented systems	Multiple, unaligned tools and paper systems	Poor data quality and duplication	Cohort tracking tools, EMIS tools and other data systems need to be harmonised and integrated

Constraint	Evidence from Findings	Implication	What should change
Weak accountability for data use	No incentives for using data in planning	Limited institutional motivation to use data	Need to embed accountability for data use within planning and performance systems
Weak feedback loops	Minimal downward flow of insights	Low learning from data	Feedback mechanisms between districts, zones and schools need to become more structured and routine

4. Policy Recommendations

The situational analysis of Malawi's foundational learning data ecosystem ([↑Saddick et al., 2025](#)) reveals a range of systemic challenges that significantly constrain the effective use of data for policy and decision-making. These challenges not only limit the availability and accessibility of relevant datasets but also impede the generation and application of evidence necessary to drive improvements in foundational learning outcomes. The recommendations below focus on practical steps to strengthen data use at school, zone, and district levels.

- **Strengthen data literacy and analytical capacity at subnational levels:** Integrate data literacy and analytical capacity into pre-service and in-service training for head teachers, teachers, primary education advisors, and district officials. Training should focus on practical tasks such as checking and improving data quality, reading trends, identifying repetition and dropout risks, and using findings to inform school and district planning.
- **Strengthen data governance, security, and protection:** Develop and enforce clear governance frameworks for the collection, storage, sharing, and use of learner-level data, including cohort tracking and learner identification numbers. This should ensure data confidentiality, controlled access across system levels, and secure data-sharing protocols in line with national data protection requirements.
- **Develop user-friendly digitised data collection and analysis tools:** Introduce dashboards and templates for school and district use, including offline solutions (e.g., mobile apps) for poor-connectivity areas.
- **Simplify and harmonise data systems:** Digitise and integrate cohort tracking data with the Annual School Census to reduce duplication, improve real-time data availability, and minimise reliance on multiple manual registers, including the class attendance and performance register, master enrolment register, and admission register. Digitisation would eliminate the need for repeated manual data entry, as data could be transferred seamlessly between registers.

- **Improve feedback mechanisms:** Establish routine feedback systems where zones and districts provide schools with termly feedback on key indicators such as enrolment trends, attendance, repetition, dropout, and learning outcomes. This feedback should be delivered through school-level meetings, cluster meetings, and district review forums and used directly to inform school improvement planning and district education planning processes.
- **Incentivise data use in decision-making:** Incorporate evidence use into performance assessments by linking performance reviews of head teachers, Primary Education Advisors, and district officials to demonstrate use of evidence in decision-making. Head teachers and officers who consistently apply data in planning and management should be recognised through existing administrative reward and performance appraisal systems.
- **Promote a culture of evidence-based decision-making:** Institutionalise data-informed school, zone, and district improvement plans by requiring plans to explicitly show which data-informed priorities and follow-up actions. This should be supported through routine termly school- and zone-level data review meetings, district planning meetings, and follow-up discussions during supervision visits.

5. Conclusion

Malawi's education system generates substantial data at subnational levels. The central challenge is now ensuring that this data is systematically used to improve decision-making and learning outcomes.

Evidence shows that the main constraints are not related to data availability but to skills, systems, and incentives for data use. Addressing these constraints requires coordinated action to strengthen data literacy, improve data systems, and embed data use into planning and accountability processes.

Priority efforts should focus on building analytical capacity at local levels, deploying simple and user-friendly data tools, strengthening feedback mechanisms, and institutionalising data use in school, zone, and district planning.

Strengthening data use at subnational levels will enable schools, zones, and districts to become active agents of improvement, supporting a more responsive, equitable, and effective education system.

6. Call for Action

The Ministry of Education and district education authorities should mandate that all school, zone, and district education plans explicitly demonstrate how data has been used to identify priorities and inform planned actions.

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These references are available digitally in our evidence library at

<https://docs.edtechhub.org/lib/79XIGS26>

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